

Thinking beyond the COVID-19 crisis: heritage-based opportunities for rural regeneration

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2. Background Information

Table 1: technical Information

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Table 2: Revision History

D	Deliverable
WP	Work Package
M	Month
RHH	Rural Heritage Hub
RM	Role Model
R	Replicator
SIA	Systemic Innovation Area
CNH	Cultural and Natural Heritage
...	

3. Executive Summary

The path towards this deliverable started at the end of 2019 when RURITAGE gathered with the H2020 funded ROCK project, working on heritage as a means for development in urban areas, at the ILUCIDARE Playground (20.11.2019 | ILUCIDARE Playground: Cracking the future of heritage). At this point, the idea to establish a common vision- a European Vision paper for urban and rural regeneration through CNH was established, as described in Task 7.3 of the Grant Agreement. Nevertheless, as the Covid-19 pandemic started in Europe in February 2020 and heavily impacted not just on daily lives of all Europeans, it also refocused importance within research and policy priorities. Thus, also in line with the Coronavirus Research and Innovation approach of the EU Commission, we decided to focus the attention on the possible consequences of Covid-19 in rural areas. Beyond the various threats and generated harmed, we aimed at highlighting community crises responses and following opportunities that arose. While it was clear from the very beginning that the first phase of the COVID-19 pandemic was considerably threatening rural areas, posing challenges exacerbated by low available financial resources, not easily accessible health services and rare and slow internet infrastructure, at the same time, in many places, rural areas have also been considered safe shelters characterized by better daily living conditions thanks to easy to maintain social distancing and access to nature, to cultural and nature-based recreation activities. While on the one side COVID-19 caused increasing rural-urban inequalities the pandemic was also then a huge opportunity to start revealing the crucial role of natural and cultural heritage for social cohesion, local development, and mental wellbeing.

For this reason, within the RURITAGE project we have looked at the main threats the current crisis is posing to rural areas, but mainly we have investigated how these challenges can be turned into opportunities for rural development and regeneration in the future.

The insights and recommendations summarized in this deliverable raised up from three activities that RURITAGE carried on:

- An open call for actions launched in April 2020 to collect practices to increase and strengthen resilience in rural communities. The call was opened from 9th of April to 18th of June and collected 66 actions from all over the world. Practices collected show how rural areas can cope with emergencies and it builds the basis to rethink the current crisis as a crucial tipping point for a resilient development of rural territories.
- A participatory workshop that took place during the RURITAGE General Assembly on May 28th, 2020, where all project partners discussed about challenges and opportunities for the future of rural areas.
- A publicly open webinar on the 8th of July 2020 to present preliminary results of this work and to discuss those with EU institutions and relevant actors in rural development (Eu Commission, Council of Europe, European Network for Rural Development).

These three activities have been framed within the RURITAGE narrative, building on heritage as a driver for rural regeneration and on the six identified Systemic Innovation Areas (Pilgrimage, Local Food Production, Art and festival, Landscape Management, Migration and Resilience), as the overall driving concept of the project. Building upon local initiatives gathered from project partners and from an open call, the range of solutions developed may not be comprehensively representative of the heterogeneity and diversity of rural areas. Nevertheless, this report aims to be a source of inspiration for rural

communities worldwide building on potential threats developed by the pandemic. Moreover, the linkages of these initiatives with the RURITAGE SIAs aims at further developing the idea that heritage-led strategies can build community resilience and contribute to inclusive and sustainable rural development.

This deliverable is based on the content of a scientific publication [‘The Covid-19 pandemic effects in rural areas- Turning challenges into opportunities for rural regeneration’](#) where we presented a first vision of future opportunities for rural areas based on current literature along with the practices collected through the open call and the RURITAGE partners’ inputs gather during the General Assembly. In this deliverable we have also integrated ideas and insights based on the discussion from the public webinar on the 8th of July 2020.

The main conclusions of this work are recommendations at European, national and local policy level, to stimulate discussion on the future of rural areas, aiming at contributing to a participated, open, and thoughtful discussion for the sustainable development of rural communities in Europe and beyond. These conclusions are summarized in a Policy brief presented in Annex I.

4. Introduction

Looking across the world, rural communities tell us the story of a thousand of years of collaboration between nature, culture, and humans. Rural areas embed unique traditions, culture, gastronomy, landscapes, and communities. Nevertheless, they are facing continuous demographic and socio-economic challenges that bring to depopulation, ageing, disengagement, reduced service provision and inhibited accessibility. Even though urban areas have been hit hard by the crisis, the current COVID-19 pandemic threatens rural areas even more, posing challenges exacerbated by low available financial resources, not easily accessible health services and greater isolation issues.

Most available scientific publication on the current COVID-19 pandemic focus on health and medical research (Fu et al., 2020; Wilson & Jack, 2020). A big share of the public debate is focusing on urban densely populated settlements, their mobility issues and the future of urban public space. Not many scholars focus on the effects, challenges and potential opportunities for rural areas caused by the crisis. According to previous studies (Setti et al., 2020; Xiao et al, 2020), the COVID-19 pandemic has a faster spread and harder impact in terms of death rate in densely populated areas with higher concentration of particulate matter, specifically PM10 and PM2.5. Yet, density is most likely just one of several key factors that determine how vulnerable places are to the virus.

Across the world, COVID-19 has taken root and strongly affected areas with diverse geographic, climatic and demographic conditions. Megacities like New York and London experience a strong impact due to large flows of visitors and tourists, diverse global populations, and dense residential areas. Also, the pandemic has been particularly serious in predominantly industrial areas like Wuhan, Detroit, and Northern Italy, that are strictly connected through supply chains and trade exchange (Florida, 2020). Rural areas have been less impacted so far, but controversies were raised in several countries (i.e Asquith, 2020) because of people that wanted to move to second houses to escape from most hit cities and regions and to enjoy calmer and more natural areas (i.e Hart, 2020).

Indeed, partial social restrictions or total lockdown experienced in some countries could have reverted citizens’ priorities. Landscape enjoyment, local safe food production and delivery, possibility of social distancing, and spread accessible open public areas, that were not much valued before, have been

increasingly acknowledged by people living in small apartments in densely populated cities (Venter et al., 2020). At the same time, several experts around the world are calling for a ‘rural renaissance’, where rural areas would assume a central role in developing sustainable and resilient communities.

As acknowledged in the recently published Communication from the Commission on the EU budget powering the recovery plan for Europe ‘rural areas will have a vital role to play in delivering the green transition and meeting Europe’s ambitious climate and environmental targets’ (European Commission, 2020). To reach this objective, the Commission is proposing to reinforce the budget for the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development by 15 billion euros. The overlying idea is to support farmers and rural areas in making the structural changes necessary to implement the European Green Deal (European Commission, 2019), and in particular to support the achievement of the ambitious targets in the new Biodiversity (European Commission, 2020b) and “Farm to Fork” strategies (European Commission, 2019).

Even if RURITAGE still acknowledges the crucial role of agriculture for the development of rural areas, it bases its regeneration paradigm on local heritage resources, perceiving heritage in its wider sense including natural and cultural heritage, beyond tangible monuments and landscapes, recognising intangible forms of traditions, social practices, and knowledge as the values that tie communities together and as a resource for sustainable local development. The whole paradigm for regenerating rural communities lies on the identification of six powerful drivers that boost regeneration in rural communities all around the world. These six drivers identified in the project are the so-called RURITAGE Systemic Innovation Areas (SIAs), namely Pilgrimage, Local Food Production, Art and festival, Landscape Management, Migration and Resilience.

Fig. 1 RURITAGE paradigm for heritage-led rural regeneration: the six Systemic Innovation Areas

Starting from the analysis of the gathered resilience practices and the fruitful brainstorming workshop, this paper attempts at giving some examples of how rural areas can cope with emergencies through the enhancement of their local, natural and cultural heritage, and it also aims at building the basis to rethink the current crisis as a crucial tipping point for a lasting resilient development of rural territories.

In this moment, when a coordinated approach on how to overcome the crisis in rural areas is missing, RURITAGE would like to propose a new strategic agenda, valuing local cultural and natural heritage to transform rural areas into long-lasting sustainable laboratories through community-built strategies for sustainable development and inclusive repopulation.

To this aim, the 5th chapter describes the process that we followed to collaboratively set up a repository of resilience practices during COVID crisis and to gain feedbacks from project partners and the wider EU community. Chapter 6th builds upon the 6 RURITAGE SIAs, underlying current challenges and potential

opportunities within the COVID-19 scenario, including the role of relevant stakeholders. The last chapter briefly discusses the results and presents the main conclusions of the paper, developing the basis to set a strategic agenda for rural sustainable development in the future and developing recommendations at different levels: European, national and regional.

5. The collaborative process

This work is an outcome of an organic collaboration within the project and beyond. Presented results are the product of multiple course of actions over months, engaging people globally. In the paragraphs below we summarized the three main steps that were taken:

- Call for action to gather rural resilience actions in the time of COVID-19
- Brainstorming workshop with RURITAGE partners at the General Assembly
- Webinar Thinking beyond the COVID-19 crisis: heritage-based opportunities for rural regeneration

5.1 The Call for Rural Resilience Actions

On the 9th of April 2020, RURITAGE launched a call for actions of knowledge, skills, ideas, and resources of social resilience across the world, with the aim of gathering and exchanging rural experiences to support each other during the COVID-19 pandemic. The call was disseminated via social media and through direct contact with project partners. In some rare cases, particularly interesting actions were contacted directly by the project and suggested to participate. In the end, the initiative received a total of number of 66 actions of rural responses from all over the globe. The call received initiatives within each RURITAGE SIA, creating a collection to aid and inspire other rural communities. The collection is found as an open resource on the [RURITAGE website](#), where the actions were gradually published under the section Rural Resilience Actions.

Actions per Country

Actions were gathered from a total of 17 countries. The countries were mostly centred within Europe: Romania, Slovenia, Finland, Sweden, Norway, United Kingdom, Ireland, France, Portugal, Spain, Italy, Greece. Actions were also received from two ENP countries: Turkey and Georgia. In addition, the call collected actions from two African countries: Kenya and Ghana. Lastly, there were two actions from Ecuador in South America. Most initiatives were received from Italy – the country where the pandemic started first in EU and was particularly tough, with a complete lockdown of a couple of months - with a total number of 22 actions. The project also received 7 actions from Spain, 6 from Turkey and 5 from both Ireland and Romania. Figure 3 illustrates the number of received actions from European countries.

Fig. 2. A cut-out of actions gathered around Europe.

Actions according to SIA

Received actions per SIAs	
Pilgrimage	2
Local Food	20
Migration	3
Art & Festivals	7
Resilience	23
Landscape management	11
Total actions	66

Fig. 3. An illustration of gathered actions according to SIA.

Most collected actions were within the Resilience SIA, with a total of 35% out of all actions. After Resilience, initiatives on Local Food, covering 30% of all actions, were gathered. The least actions were received within the SIA of pilgrimage, with only 3% of all actions.

Actions according to Cross-cutting themes

Fig. 4. An illustration of collected actions in accordance to cross-cutting themes.

To better understand which issues were tackled by the various initiatives all the collected actions were clustered into the multiple cross-cutting themes, identified within the RURITAGE project, in accordance to the topics they touch on. Cultural and natural heritage was the most commonly approached theme, followed by social innovation. The least touched upon cross-cutting themes were Energy and climate change mitigation and adaptation, that can be considered less related to the crisis together with Tourism and marketing strategies. Considering that tourism is one of the most affected sectors due to lockdowns, social distancing and the tightened borders. As most activities related to tourism were called off there

were not many alternative solutions, at least during the first intense spread of the pandemic, that could be proposed to face the lack of movements imposed by the restriction measures. See figure 5 for a full overview of the cross-cutting themes.

5.2 The Brainstorming workshops at the RURITAGE General Assembly

During the RURITAGE General Assembly, that took place online on the 27th and 28th of May, project partners participated to a brainstorming session on rural challenges and opportunities presented by the COVID19 crisis (May 27th). The discussion had been initiated prior the meeting on RURITAGE Digital Rural Heritage Hub (DRHH), a project tool used to open discussions and gather first thoughts and comments regarding three main questions:

- 1) Which are the main challenges and opportunities presented by the actual crisis in rural with respect to the identified SIAs?
- 2) What are the main challenges and needs of your local stakeholders? How can we support them within RURITAGE?
- 3) Which ideas do you have in mind?

During the brainstorming, three parallel sessions have been organized, coupling two SIAs per session:

- Pilgrimage and Landscape
- Art&Festival and Local Food production
- Resilience and Migration

The three sessions have been organized and moderated by the project coordination team at UNIBO and hosted a total of 74 participants of the 38 project partners.

Fig. 5. An extract from the session on Pilgrimage and Landscape.

Each session lasted for around 40 minutes and participants were asked to move from one session to another to cover all the different SIAs. This ‘world café’ modality allowed to have smaller groups (up to 20-25 people) to facilitate discussions and interactions.

The Invision tool - embedded in the Microsoft Teams software that was used for the online meeting - was used to set the interactive Board where participants were asked to contribute. The Board was initially set up by the moderators of each session including ideas coming from the DRHH and from available literature. After a short presentation of main ideas collected through the DRRH and already included in the Board, participants were asked to add their thoughts on colourful post it and to discuss them together. When entering into a new session, delegates were asked to reflect on their colleagues’ prior thoughts from the internal forum, visualised on the screen, and to further write down additional challenges and opportunities. This resulted in an eager exchange of experiences, viewpoints and opportunities.

5.3 Joint Webinar: Thinking beyond the COVID-19 crisis: heritage-based opportunities for rural regeneration

To build synergies with similar initiatives at EU level, RURITAGE organized a public webinar that was held on the 8th of July on the theme: "Thinking beyond the COVID-19 crisis: heritage-based opportunities for rural regeneration".

RURITAGE project coordinator discussed this issue with representatives from the EU Commission (DG AGRI, DG RTD and EASME), the Council of Europe, and the European Network for Rural

Fig. 6. A print screen from the joint webinar together with some of the delegates.

Development (ENRD). Stefano Dominioni,

Executive Secretary of the Enlarged Partial Agreement on Cultural Routes of the Council of Europe (EPA) and Director of the European Institute of Cultural Routes (Luxembourg) spoke about "*The Cultural Routes of the Council of Europe programme: Tools for rural regeneration in the post-Covid 19 context*". Dominioni was followed by Flavio Conti, Policy Analyst, from the European Network for Rural Development (ENRD) on "*Rural responses to the COVID-19 crisis in Europe*", and ENRD's work to create a platform for rural development stakeholders during the crisis. After, Maciej W. Hofman, Policy Officer at the European Commission's Directorate-General for Education, Youth, Sport and Culture (DG EAC) spoke about "*EU cultural policy and culture in rural areas: current topics and upcoming initiatives*". Hofman was followed by a joint presentation between Giulia Facelli, Policy Officer on 'Innovating Cities' at the European Commission DG RTD, and Victoria Beaz Hidalgo, Senior Project Adviser at the European Commission's Executive Agency for Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (EASME). Together they presented "*R&I and Horizon 2020 initiatives to tackle COVID-19 crisis*". Lastly, Helen Williams from the Commission's Directorate-General for Agriculture and Rural Development (DG AGRI) she presented an: "*Overview of Commission Coronavirus response initiatives relevant for agriculture and rural areas*".

More than 100 participants joined the more than two-hours long webinar from all over Europe and beyond, from local stakeholders, action initiators, and representatives from different universities and various institutions. During the presentations, there was an active discussion taking place in the chat, further sharing experiences, inputs, and knowledge. The full webinar together with all presentations can be found on the RURITAGE website under webinars (<https://www.ruritage.eu/resources/webinars/>).

6. COVID-19 effects in RURITAGE Systemic Innovation Areas: challenges and opportunities

To participate to the ongoing discussion on Covid-19 in relation to urban and rural planning, the insights gathered from Brainstorming workshop (section 4.1.1) and Call for Rural Resilience actions (section 4.1.2) were turned into an academic journal paper.

The paper 'The COVID-19 pandemic effects in rural areas -Turning challenges into opportunities for rural regeneration' was published in a special issue of TeMA - Journal of Land Use, Mobility and Environment on the 19th of June 2020¹. It was one out twenty-seven contributes of international researchers approaching present circumstances and insights in relation to Covid-19. The paper mainly discussed how the current Covid-19 pandemic is threatening rural areas by posing challenges due to low financial resources, inaccessible health services and great social isolation. Further, it argued for the Covid-19 crisis to be revealing the crucial role of natural and cultural heritage for social cohesion, local development and mental wellbeing. It aimed to show how rural areas can cope with emergencies, building the basis to rethink the current crisis as a crucial tipping point for a resilient development of rural territories. This section is based on the outcome of the paper, adding action cards with examples of the more interesting or innovative initiatives that have been collected through the RURITAGE Call for Actions.

6.1 Pilgrimage

The tourism sector directly contributes to 4.4% of GDP, 6.9% of employment and 21.5% of service exports in OECD countries, on average, and continued growth provides real prospects for sustainable and inclusive development (OECD, 2020b). Prior to the COVID-19 outbreak, the travel and tourism sectors were expected to make up 10% of global Gross Domestic Product (GDP) in Europe (European Commission, 2020d). Pilgrimage, holy and hiking routes are currently valuable options of sustainable and slow tourism in Europe and all over the world (Balestrieri & Congiu, 2017; Nolan & Nolan, 1992). Within RURITAGE, the cases of Camino de Santiago (Spain) and Via Mariae (Romania) demonstrate how rediscovering local cultural and natural heritage along pilgrimage and hiking routes poses great opportunities for less explored areas to gain recognition and boost local economy.

As easily understood, the tourism and travel sectors have been particularly hit hard by the crisis. According to a survey conducted by Cultural Routes Programme of the Council of Europe, 70% of the cultural routes are expected COVID-19 to affect budget and functioning beyond 2020 (Council of Europe, 2020). The European Union's tourism industry is estimated to lose around one billion euros in revenue per month because of the outbreak (European Commission, 2020d). The Travel & Tourism sector faces a staggering 100 million jobs losses due to the coronavirus pandemic, according to the World Travel & Tourism Council. The impact on the travel and tourism ecosystem particularly hit the small and medium enterprises sectors.

¹ <http://www.tema.unina.it/index.php/tema/article/view/6844>

Remote spiritual guidance

 Harghita, Romania

Through providing mother tongue pastoral care services for minorities and online masses, the aim is to promote mental health protection while encouraging awareness of spiritual protection and emotional development in rural areas. One activity is the online pastoral work where people can continue to join the masses without leaving their house. During holidays they provide practical information for home-celebration including infographics, songs, and suggest activities. Another important initiative is spiritual guidance, both via a telephone and online services with volunteers.

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Learn more here: https://www.ruritage.eu/resilience-actions/spiritual-_guidance_online/

Figure 7. An online poster for the spiritual guidance.

This crisis is creating huge challenges also to the pilgrimage and hiking routes because of travel restrictions on the one side, and also due to the intrinsic cross-border nature of some religious pilgrimage route and events, such as the Hajj in Islam and Santiago de Compostela in Catholicism that draw millions of pilgrims every year. Ensuring health and safety of local populations and of pilgrims in such emergencies could be quite challenging (Escher, 2020) while small hotels, business working in the food and beverage sectors could struggle in adapting to the current safety measures imposed by local governments. On the other hand, most of the less known pilgrimage and hiking routes – that could better face the issue of managing lower numbers of tourists - dispose of limited financial resources, that could be further reduced because of the current crisis.

At the same time, if properly planned and managed, pilgrimage and hiking routes can be considered amongst the safest tourism destinations in the current COVID-19 crisis, thanks to the intrinsic nature of such activities that can easily adapt to the current imposed social distancing rules and that naturally take place in open-air natural environment, thus facilitating their adaptation to the current challenge.

It is therefore crucial to raise a great coordination among all involved and interested stakeholders, from regional to local authorities to local businesses involved in the activities – mainly hotels, restaurants and other accommodations structures – to guarantee the adoption of appropriate measures for safe destination, keeping small local and family-run businesses alive. Big opportunities are raising both for internationally recognized pilgrimage and hiking routes, that could redirect their targets towards family and domestic tourists, and also for smaller and less known places that can claim for the re-discovering of local cultural and natural heritage, involving rural communities into long-lasting regeneration process. Also, pilgrimage and hiking could take this chance to connect to other nature-related activities – i.e. open-air sports, fishing, etc. – that will support market diversification increasing the potential number

of visitors of the area. In some cases, i.e. KATLA Geopark in Iceland, they are taking the chance of this moment, when there are no visitors entering the country - to improve and re-develop part of the pilgrimage related infrastructures also temporarily employing people that lost their jobs due to the crisis. Finally, current limitations to big mass events and crowded hotspots, are calling for a spread tourist offer during the upcoming seasons that could be boosted and sustainably maintained through time by involving and engaging with the creative sectors' local stakeholders and organizing small events along the pilgrimage and hiking routes, such as small concert, open air movies, theatre representations.

In the same spirit, the Cultural Routes Programme argue that cultural routes can be a catalyst for rural regeneration post-COVID-19 by ensuring safety in destinations, promoting sustainable initiatives, giving visibility to rural areas, and developing synergies between routes. Moreover, cultural routes can possibly attract visitors to less known destination, be a way to implement innovative approaches, and promote economic development through offering authentic experiences, reducing seasonality and tourism pressure, increased measures for heritage and landscape preservation, and extending tourist stays (Council of Europe, 2020). All this will be possible only thanks to a strong and coordinated responses by the whole pilgrimage and hiking routes, able to involve the whole stakeholder chain.

6.2 Local Food

Sustainable food and drinks production and local gastronomy embody agricultural practices, rural landscape, local history and traditions, and symbolizes the cultural heritage of a territory. Food serves as a strong connection between nature and human society bringing together land, heritage and the people. As in the case of RURITAGE Role Models, the Coffee Landscape of Colombia and the local Agro-food production in Puglia, local food production is a diverse and dynamic channel for sharing stories, forming relationships, create development and building communities. While food production is mostly located in rural areas, population is increasingly living in densely populated urban areas (Seto et al., 2017) far away from places where the food is actually produced. In the last decades, the global food trade changed the eating habits of consumers which moved from local and retail markets to supermarkets and discount stores. Moreover, the significant change in lifestyle, the increase in working hours, and the decreasing availability of time to cook, led to triumph of supermarkets, fast food services and discount store (Cappelli & Cini, 2020). On the other side, a huge movement in slow food production and consumption, healthy lifestyle and zero kilometres philosophy is rising.

The current COVID-19 emergency re-opened the discussion on food security in Europe which seemed to be distant memories due to shortage in agricultural workers (Hobbs, 2020; News European Parliament, 2020) and issues in food transportation and global logistic (Gray, 2020). There is a well-known issue concerning the lack of agricultural workers that has resulted in unharvested and unsold stock. Food producers and farmers are currently greatly challenged to find temporary workers due to travel restrictions. However, there are recognised ethical challenges of temporary labour for agriculture where workers are often treated differently than inhabitants (Chung, 2019). Instead of temporary labour, there are opportunities to enable formal engagement for workers.

Home delivery of Local products

Campania, Italy; Machynlleth, UK;
Harghita, Romania;
Koroška, Slovenia

Food delivery actions look different depending on where they have been initiated. It has often been a question of adaption and finding new ways for local businesses to cooperate to jointly reach and maintain their customers by creating a network. This covers all kinds of local entrepreneurs from bookstores to bakeries, or all e.g. dairy producers. Some businesses have made their usual products possible to order via their homepages, directly through Facebook pages where the customer can place an order via the farmer's Facebook. In other areas, local authorities have stepped in to gather products on designated pages.

Figure 8. The online page of a bakery in Machynlleth, UK.

Learn more here: https://www.ruritage.eu/resilience-actions/local_home_deliveries/

On the top of this, a report coming from the UK (Loopstra, 2020) described how the COVID-19 lockdown not only exacerbated food insecurity among those who regularly struggle, but also created new economic vulnerabilities due to loss of work and income, or even because people are self-isolating and unable to get the food they need. This situation created several private solidarity actions, where businesses, public sectors and the civil society have teamed up together to provide services to the local communities. In Izmir, Turkey, the municipality has stepped into support at the same time local food producers and vulnerable people and families. They developed food-aid packages containing locally produced food that are funded by private donations either online or directly in stores. The municipality delivers packages directly to vulnerable groups and economically disadvantaged families. In this way, less benefited members of society are supported as well as the local entrepreneurs and farmers. Also, in areas where initiatives have not been directly coordinated by authorities, local food producers and farmers are forced to rethink and adapt their businesses. Across rural Europe, many initiatives for distributing food directly from the producers to the customers' homes are taking place. The initial aim has often been to maintain an active production in order to adapt to current challenges. But at the same time, by receiving deliveries to the door, inhabitants are less exposed to risk. This is both a way to ensure the health of vulnerable inhabitants but also an action to strengthen local production and entrepreneurs. For elderly and vulnerable groups this action can be a potential lifesaver. The action of food delivery has taken different shapes depending on where it has been initiated and the kind of local entrepreneurs,

producers, and farmers. Most businesses have made their usual products possible to order via their homepages or directly by phone. In other areas, initiatives have arisen from networks of local farmers, through the support of social networks, where customers can place an order via Facebook pages, while in others there was a top-down approach achieved in cooperation with regional authorities. Another model has been to list local producers on the municipality website where the inhabitants can easily reach and buy local food/products directly from the manufacturer.

The Mobile Market

Izmir, Turkey

The municipality of Izmir buys locally produced food from farmers nearby. The food is then distributed and sold via Mobil Market vehicles that go around the territory of Izmir. The municipality ensures fair prices for costumers and salaries for the producers. With the Mobile Market, inhabitants who cannot go to the market due to the epidemic can do their grocery shopping at right in front of peoples' doors.

Figure 9. The Mobile Market delivers directly at the door.

Learn more here: https://www.ruritage.eu/resilience-actions/mobile_market/

Both in urban and rural areas the crisis sped up and supported the development of new business models based on sustainable door-to-door food delivery. It is now crucial to work on the sustainability of these new business models as these logistic innovations towards online commerce of food can arguably be an excellent opportunity to reach and maintain new customers for local food producers. In rural areas, there is a need of further developing local capacity and skills towards digital tools for advertisement, logistic and e-products. Local authorities and relevant stakeholders – small farmers and local producer associations - could build upon this new trend to boost the capacity of local farmers through on online training and educational tools as well as interactive webinars to spread knowledge. In the medium-long term, this change of perspective could increase awareness of food independence in communities and it can also contribute to develop a greater trust-building between local farmers and inhabitants. Also, through the crisis, there is a high potential of reinforcing the role of local producers and farmers and to boost the recognition of local communities' bond with their territories. The reinforcement of such relations could enhance the local microeconomy also in non-crisis situations, since it allows to increase local employment and improve people's quality of life (Cappelli & Cini, 2020), contributing to the regeneration of rural territories. The crisis has highlighted the importance of the rural world as the food producer for the sustainability of life and the deep relations between the urban and rural worlds. Rural areas should not lose this opportunity but start to work on this further in relation with the closest peri-urban and urban areas, building and reinforcing existing Short and Slow Food Ecosystems of relevant producers, consumers and other stakeholders.

6.3 Migration

Beyond the challenges presented by the migration crisis, migrant arrivals in rural contexts serves as a great opportunity for rural regeneration (Green et al., 2009; Greve Harbo, Lisbeth; Ström Hildestrand, Åsa; Heleniak, Timothy; Sigurjónsdóttir, 2017). Indeed, despite the challenges posed, rural areas can take advantage of the opportunities provided by an influx of migrants as a source of new vitality to restore declining villages. In areas suffering from population decline and closing services, the arrival of migrants can create new opportunities for growth.

This is the case of Lesvos UNESCO Global Geopark (GR), that has developed integration and information programs for newly arrived as well as citizens on local cultural and natural heritage and of PIAM Onlus (IT), that works on migrant's hospitality and inclusion in Asti province, also rediscovering the autochthonous varieties of ancient wheat as local food and heritage as a way for boosting migrants' integration (Conticelli et al., 2019) through the connection with local food, territory and traditions. They have demonstrated that it is possible to boost and accelerate the process of integration and regeneration by means of (i) integrating migrants within the local agro-food chain and the creative industries, (ii) restoring old and unused buildings to give hospitality to the migrants, (iii) offering training to migrants and residents related with organic farming, arts, built heritage restoration, traditional crafts and trades, etc. (iv) facilitating the connection with residents with defined food- (ethnic cuisine) and art-related activities (traditional dance, music performance), (v) offering internships for migrants in local businesses, farms, tourism related activities, (vi) developing integration and information programmes for migrants and citizens, (vii) offering educational programmes and guided tours, specifically tailored for migrants to make them aware of the cultural and natural heritage of the territory.

The COVID-19 pandemic has posed new challenges to the areas hosting migrants and refugees, because of the need to stop many integration activities (i.e. language courses, work on the field) due to total or partial lockdown measures, thus in some cases exacerbating already existing problems. Many government services have been suspended because of the ongoing coronavirus pandemic. To help approximately 220,000 migrants in Germany resume their lessons, the Federal Office for Migration and Refugees has invested about 40 millions of euros to continue the courses in a digital format and currently, nearly 83,000 immigrants are participating in digital integration and language courses (Bathke, 2020). As social distancing rules and guidelines have been implemented across Europe, authorities and migrant associations have expressed concerns about the living conditions of some of the most vulnerable members of society. In Italy, migrants living in reception centres have written an open letter to authorities expressing their concerns about living in close, confined spaces and officials have voiced concerns about the conditions of asylum seeker camps on the Greek islands (European Commission, 2020c). On the other hand, the imposed sanitation measures forced all reception centres to adopt adequate sanitation, including the ones that did not have acceptable quality levels before the emergency. In this sense, the pandemic could boost the finding of a permanent solution to overcrowded asylum camps and low living conditions.

One crucial part of the response to the COVID-19 pandemic is to make sure that all members of society have the information they need to stay healthy and follow quarantine guideline (World Health Organisation (WHO), 2020b). To ensure that migrants are not overlooked in the response, civil society organisations have been busy translating and communicating vital information to their communities. Authorities have also made an effort to communicate critical information in multiple languages

(European Commission, 2020c). Moreover, support measures to improve communication and counter xenophobia have been activated in many areas in order to provide accurate and timely evidence-based information, aiming at dispelling fears and misperceptions among host populations regarding refugees or migrants and the COVID-19 outbreak (World Health Organisation (WHO), 2020a).

Because of the pandemic, countries have tightened their borders and restricted the entry of most foreign nationalities. This has strongly affected some economic sectors, and mainly the agricultural one that strongly relies on seasonal migrant farm workers. COVID-19 has also posed controversial challenges to migrant domestic workers. For some, workload has increased, and free Sundays have been denied as the whole family is staying at home and is demanding more constant assistance. Others have been let go by employers confined at home, refusing contact with outsiders (Jordan and Dickerson, 2020; IOM-CREST, 2020).

Integration of migrants in fields and vineyards

Asti, Italy

Migrants, through integrated reception paths with the territory is an important aid of local development. For increased integration and boost rural development, the province of Asti encourages newly arrived migrants to work together with local farmers. COVID-19 is challenging the workforce within agriculture, with farmers finding it difficult to hire workers. Examples such as this can help to improve integration and aid local farmers by employing migrants in the agricultural sector where labour force is scarce.

Figure 10. An image from a vineyard in Asti

Learn more here: <https://www.ruritage.eu/resilience-actions/migrants-in-the-fields/>

In some countries, like for instance in Canada, temporary migrant workers were among those permitted entry; they have been deemed essential workers due to the central role they play in supporting Canadian farmers and the food supply (Hastie, 2020). In Italy, to find a solution to the urgent need for farm workers, PIAM Onlus has promoted an agreement with farmers organizations, through which refugees are employed in the agriculture sector under the supervision of the managers of reception centres. These procedures involve regular working agreements, therefore counteracting illegal exploitative activities (a phenomenon that is known as "caporalato" in Italy).

The pandemic has thus emphasized that migrant workers (farm workers, but also workers in health sector and migrant caregivers, etc.), are essential to the local economy due to their expertise and skills. As highlighted by the Communication from the Commission "Guidelines concerning the exercise of the free movement of workers during COVID-19 outbreak" (European Commission, 2020a) it is necessary that those workers are treated in the same manner as the workers that exercise critical occupations referred to above. Beyond allowing such workers to continue crossing the borders, it also needed to

guarantee that the employers provide them for adequate health and safety protection. Identifying and disseminating good practices, strengthening dialogue and coordination between recruiters and employers, and stimulating business action in global supply chains to effectively protect migrant worker health, well-being and rights, could definitely enhance the commitment and capacity of employers and labour recruiters to protect migrant workers, including seasonal workers, not only during the pandemic but also after the end of the emergency, and thus could help in addressing improving the future integration of migrants in local communities.

6.4 Art&Festival

Cultural and creative sectors tend to be considered less accessible for rural communities. By enabling participants of all ages and abilities to take part in artistic activities, RURITAGE intends to use culture, art and festival as a mean to further increase territories' attractivity, creativity and to eventually revitalize local communities. Accordingly, RURITAGE clearly aspires to make the arts more accessible to rural communities to experience, participate, and work in.

The cultural and creative industries is one of the sectors most heavily affected by the COVID-19, with performances and concerts cancelled, and theatres, museums, and cinemas that have been closed. As in urban areas, cultural life and social exchange in rural areas is halted. SMEs are largely affected by the COVID-19; in Italy, for example, approximately a third of SMEs in the creative sector will suffer from a 15% decline (OECD, 2020a). According to a preliminary estimation by Eurostat, the COVID-19 crisis might affect about 7.3 million cultural jobs across the EU. Over 30% of the affected workers are self-employed and lack adequate social protection (EU Science Hub, 2020). On the 27 March 2020 the Culture and Education Committee Chair, Sabine Verheyen, stated that the cultural and creative sectors across Europe have been disrupted by the impact of stringent public health measures. Verheyen claimed that cultural and creative businesses are among those struggling the most and in most need of financial support. Under the Coronavirus Response Investment Initiative, European Member States will be able to use Structural Funds money to support small businesses and employment schemes. Verheyen asserted that businesses and individuals in the cultural and creative sector should receive access to this financial support (European Parliament, 2020). As there is no common strategy on EU level yet, most EU countries have developed own approaches. For instance, Italy has set an emergency fund addressed to performing arts, cinema and audio-visual media and has removed taxes for cultural sites. At the same time, in Denmark, there is a funding coverage of 75% of cultural work salaries (EUNIC Global, 2020). Rural access to creativity and culture has not been explicitly mentioned in any of such initiatives.

Although culture has already been accessible online for many years, the globally occurring lockdown made virtual access the only way to approach culture. Many significant cultural institutes have moved partly online as a way to boost and enrich reality. The biggest European museums designed online tours allowing visitors to see parts of the collections, while smaller venues are following. Culture in rural areas has not been at the centre of this debate. Nevertheless, in rural areas, libraries have made their collections available online where some have even provided videos of librarians reading out loud directly to children. The same applies for rural-based festivals, where some will instead manifest themselves virtually (Rowen, 2020). However, digital tools are not only used by grander organizations but also by smaller art groups, study circles or networks which continue meeting virtually while performing and executing their art. An example of this is a smaller study circle on the island Gotland, Sweden, where

seniors paint together virtually on a weekly basis. By encouraging societal groups to sustain their usual practices but in a new format can help to maintain a sense of community in rural areas.

Vattenmålarna: connecting creativity

Gotland, Sweden

Vattenmålarna is a group of seniors that meet and paint every week. Due to the COVID-19 emergence, Vattenmålarna have initiated weekly online meetings where they paint together. The aim is to maintain a sense of community and continue to creatively express themselves in a difficult time. Most of them paint pictures interpreting their current situation, for example, 'missing my grandchildren or 'imagining being outside again'. The group aims to make an exhibition, in what format is not clear yet but hopefully virtually.

Figure 11. A painting of some of the group members

Learn more here: <https://www.ruritage.eu/resilience-actions/vattenmalarna/>

The effect of abandoning tangible experiences for the benefits of online participation should also be noted. Although digitalization is generally conceived as an opportunity, increasing accessibility and connectivity, it has its limitations. By bringing culture online there is a risk of creating something excluding, in particular in rural areas where there is a lower access to internet connection. There is also a lower usability among an older population, who often constitute a noticeable part of rural inhabitants. In this case, accessibility may turn into unapproachability, depending on technological access and skills. In regard of this, it is suggested that the online activities are mainly complimentary means (Kuźelewska & Tomaszuk, 2020) The urge for tangible art experiences and social exchange can be stressed as a result of post-isolation and social distancing. The fear of disease transmission can also pose for more vulnerable groups both physical and psychological problems that go beyond government regulations and that could lead to exacerbate vulnerability and exclusion.

At the same time, there may be an emergence of other type of events and gatherings. The easiest solutions approached by several local authorities is to create a spread offer of open- air events with smaller audiences and closer contact. However, the questions on how limited audiences would affect the ticket prices and the affordability for locals should be raised. The demand for arts will perhaps increase and offer more frequent opportunities for artists to perform and for locals to take part in performances. For example, interactive transformational festivals can be sustainable opportunity for people of all ages explore, participate and work within (Rowen, 2020). By developing more flexible “menus” of art and festivals for communities, adapting to local needs, conditions and practices, a more sustainable rural cultural exploration may emerge.

The state of emergency at local level has forced to redirect resources towards the health care systems, in order to respond to the most urgent needs, leaving little room to the cultural sector, in lack of an EU

strategy. The crisis can arguably have caused a fear of widening social inequality while revealed the crucial role of culture for cohesion and mental wellbeing. However, the current restrictions can be viewed as an opportunity to strengthen the rural arts and festival scene from within. Reinforcement of the local scene can possibly enhance the local sense of recognition and further on interest in heritage and history. The restrictions may even allow local artists to gain greater appreciation and therethrough, lead to a regeneration of the local art scene and provide a catalyst for creative grassroots projects where the outcome might be a social meeting place for locals which creates a sense of belonging and pride within the rural communities.

Storytelling with children

Castelvetro, Italy

Every day, the library in Castelvetro publishes videos of librarians and volunteers reading books on their Facebook page. The initial aim of the action is to encourage children to read more.

In the time the pandemic, the service provides a great opportunity for children to leave worries about their new daily life for the splendour of books.

Figure 12. A part of the volunteers.

Learn more here: https://www.ruritage.eu/resilience-actions/storytelling_with_children/

6.5 Resilience

RURITAGE explores the concept of resilience as driver of regeneration, turning challenges in learning and development opportunities, by enhancing the role of cultural and natural heritage for building resilience against the threats of climate change, natural disasters and social and economic crisis, simultaneously boosting economic growth, creating jobs and livelihoods, strengthening access to health and education, and contributing to foster the responsible ownership of cultural and natural heritage in rural areas. Within RURITAGE, Psiloritis UNESCO Global Geopark (GR) and KATLA UNESCO Global Geopark (IS) are good examples of how responsible ownership of cultural and natural heritage in rural areas can turn a challenge as a natural disaster into an opportunity for revitalizing the rural territory basing on participative projects, on resilience training for the community and on traditional storytelling as a mean to understand the environment, foster awareness on the relation among landscape, hazards

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and man's interventions. The COVID-19 crisis has highlighted that new crises of unforeseeable nature are likely to emerge, as the combination of environmental degradation, societies with increasing inequalities and deep economic interconnections have made the world more vulnerable, thus underlining the need to approach societal resilience from a 360-degrees system approach (Giovannini et al., 2020). The COVID-19 shock is so extreme in its duration and intensity that it is simply impossible to address it through absorptive capacities or a simple adaptation of the system. Therefore, it should become an opportunity to progress and "bounce forward" through adaptation and transformation (Giovannini et al., 2020).

Providing E-Learning services

 Tetriskaro, Georgia

Access to technology and internet is an issue for many families in the villages of Tetriskaro. As a long-term solution introduced by the organisation RDFG is Distance Services Including E-Learning tools for rural school students, young entrepreneurs/farmers, and vocational training/skills development sessions. This assure children's rights to education and strengthen the community through the support of socially vulnerable families by providing basic technology.

Figure 13. Two young children in Tetriskaro.

Learn more here: <https://www.ruritage.eu/resilience-actions/providing-e-learning-services/>

The lack of fast internet connection, already considered a crucial hamper in the development of rural territories, could be one of the main barriers to allow smooth and fast communication, creating trouble in distance learning for pupils and smart-working for adults and contribute to make rural inhabitants even more isolated during the lock-down measures. Also, people in rural areas are suffering of more severe mobility issues, due to social distances and private cars' use restrictions. Reaching rural areas in the time of crisis was and still is much more difficult than it was before. At the same time, social distancing, the lack of adequate open public green areas and the possibility of smart-working or working from home could drive people living in densely populated settlements to look for moving to more natural environments. In most cases, rural areas have proved to be safe shelters compared to urban agglomerations: a lower rate of infection and better daily living conditions during confinement. This perception could lead to big opportunities for repopulating ageing rural areas, and to make rural areas attractive poles of development. Some rural areas are already thinking about developing co-working space with fast internet connection to host digital and nomad workers in their territories. This process represents a huge opportunity but could also lead to an unplanned gentrification issue. Indeed, urban smart workers tend to have much higher income than rural inhabitants and could speed up a rural

gentrification process. To avoid such unwanted consequences, this process should be carefully planned and managed by local administration. Improve services and infrastructures – both for mobility and internet connections - for rural inhabitants is crucial to create long-lasting communities of people that decide to stay, live and work in rural territories.

The Rossie Way

Roscommon, Ireland

The Rossie Way community radio aims to reach people in higher-risk groups, especially in rural areas who tend to be isolated due to the severe restrictions placed on them. They provide daily radio programming by volunteer producers and DJs to build resilience in the local community. through a mix of music, chat, local celebrity interviews, local guests, quizzes, special requests, and online religious ceremonies. The common theme is a positive message to keep company to its audience.

Figure 14. Radios were distributed to elderly.

Learn more here: <https://www.ruritage.eu/resilience-actions/community-radio/>

Moreover, the need to face a completely new scenario lead to invent new ways to contribute to health, training and education of the population, thus empowering the human capital, i.e. through improved the skills and abilities of people to develop and enhance their resources. COVID-19 emergency showed, even more clearly than before, that to boost digital skills in the local community is a real priority. The main challenges that both urban and rural areas are currently facing is the need to recover activities after the pandemic in safe conditions and to give children the possibility to attend educational and social activities while schools are closed. With reference to the former, business and local activities had to face both a great loss of revenue, for which financial support by the governments is needed, and the adoption of measures to guarantee safety conditions and the respect of social distancing among workers and users that are not always clear and that make it difficult to understand what needs to be done. Moreover, to implement the safety measures, costs are needed that small businesses are not able to sustain and for this reason they prefer to remain closed. On the other hand, new economic activities linked to the crisis have born and could become permanent. In Ireland, for instance, a collect-and-deliver service offer services from pharmacies and local shops for passengers, delivering critical medical supplies for the elderly, the vulnerable, and the sick within rural areas. Finally, after a long period of “home-schooling” and social distancing, new measures are needed to give children the chance to safely attend educational and social activities.

Connecting hearts

Aguilar de Campoo, Spain

Ensure mental wellbeing and strengthen the community by maintaining a social connection for all age groups. The aim is to provide a virtual exchange experience between high school freshmen at a local high school and elderly people at a nursing home. The purpose is to strengthen the links between youth and the elderly, to spread awareness of local challenges, to stay connected and to learn from the shared experience. The elderly has shown to truly enjoy the company of the students as the connections are like windows to the world.

Figure 15. A senior speaking to a freshman via digital tools.

Learn more here: https://www.ruritage.eu/resilience-actions/connecting_hearts

To turn the COVI-19 crisis into a new opportunity or revitalization for total areas, opening up new possibilities of counterbalancing depopulation and ageing characterizing many rural areas, policy measures are needed able to provide better infrastructures (physical and technological) for guaranteeing the physical and technological accessibility to the areas. Strengthening digitalization, training, sustainability combined with a stronger local financial capital, represents strategic measures to support people and local community.

Support the most vulnerable in society

Izmir, Turkey

In Izmir, the municipality has stepped in to support local food producers directly through the launch of the campaign “We are There“. By setting up food aid packages, funded via donations online or directly in stores, the municipality delivers packages directly to vulnerable groups and economically disadvantaged families. In this way, less benefited members of society are supported as well as the local entrepreneurs and farmers.

Figure 16. Volunteer packaging food packages.

Learn more here: https://www.ruritage.eu/resilience-actions/support_vulnerable/

6.6 Landscape management

RURITAGE not only intends landscape as cultural or protected landscape, but more as rural territories with multi-level governance, and heritage-based planning and management strategies. The cases of the Wild Atlantic Way (IE), the Duero-Douro cultural landscape (ES,PT) and the Austrått and Ørland, manorial landscape (NO) well represent example of diverse integrated landscape management and governance models that boosted regional development through their natural and cultural heritage. Even though rural areas may have been less hardly hit by the pandemic, the current COVID-19 crisis is presenting huge challenges to regions that are trying to boost rural regeneration through dedicated networks, funds and agreed strategies and visions. At the same time there is a shared fear that funds dedicated to rural development and environmental protection may be reduced in the following years and reallocated to more urgent public sectors (i.e health, education, etc.), even though European Union is working on increasing the European Agricultural Fund for rural development. This would of course further exacerbate existing unemployment and issues, forcing even more rural inhabitant to move to urban areas.

TeachOut : Bringing people outdoor

Magma, Norway

TeachOut is an outdoor science game that aims to get young inhabitants outside and enjoy and learn about their surrounding landscape. TeachOut is a mobile app based on analysis of national school curricula and then adapted by teachers to be used by their students. TechOut allows nature to be the classroom where students are given questionnaires, treasure hunts, experiments, drawing tasks and competitions.

Figure 17. A student using Teachout.

Learn more here: https://www.ruritage.eu/resilience-actions/digital_tours/

Also, the values of the natural and cultural capitals of rural territory have not been altered, and this offers good opportunity to offer safe and beautiful tourist and work destination. The reduction of tourists has given a respite to those areas that received more visitors, favouring their ecological recovery. In this sense, regional and local authorities a have a great occasion to increase the value of their natural capital integrating ecosystem and their services into decision making process and local policies. In line with the EU Green New Deal (European Commission, 2019), local authorities and stakeholders could use this moment to focus on shaping a more sustainable future rethinking how 'to protect, conserve and

enhance the EU's natural capital, and protect the health and well-being of citizens from environment-related risks and impacts'. Also, as mentioned in the recently released EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 (European Commission, 2020b) 'the recent COVID- 19 pandemic makes the need to protect and restore nature all the more urgent. The pandemic is raising awareness of the links between our own health and the health of ecosystems'. Investing in green infrastructure, wellness corridor, and slow mobility infrastructure can on the one side improve and restore natural ecosystem, but at the same time creating options for sustainable tourism.

Regional governments, tourism agencies, cluster of innovators in heritage and landscape management have a great opportunity to rethink tourism in a more sustainable way and to work on the peculiar characteristics on their areas. Indeed, rural territories have now the possibility to develop their distinctive characteristics, building on their natural and cultural heritage resources and enhancing human capitals.

Digital tours in Psiloritis Geopark

Crete, Greece

In Psiloritis Geopark, digital visiting has become available. By providing the opportunity to tour the geopark from a distance, locals, as well as non-locals, are now able to visit even the most distant parts of the geopark, directly from their home. Local food and craft producers have also gained promotion through this initiative. The geopark has developed an interactive map presenting all the natural and cultural features of the geopark together with local products and activities. The online tools include also a storytelling map that offers stories and information of the geopark through video and music.

Learn more here: https://www.ruritage.eu/resilience-actions/digital_tours/

Cultural and nature-based tourism is increasingly growing in the last decade and it is very likely that it will keep growing after the COVID-19 pandemic. Working on an integrated management of the landscape and heritage could support regions and rural territories to find their local distinctiveness and identity, building their own local brand for regeneration. There is arguably a great opportunity to create or reinforced existing networks to build a community response around a common purpose.

7. Discussion and Conclusions

Fragmented responses to the COVID-19 challenges for rural areas are starting to raise around EU and beyond through reinforced networks, better collaboration, cooperation and solidarity for strengthened resilience.

What emerges for the analysis of the collected initiatives and actions is that local communities need to use and manage in an integrated way the five capitals (cultural, social, human, built and financial) to achieve success. Specifically, in most of the cases, human and social capitals are the first drivers of the change able to turn the crisis into an opportunity. Interestingly, this corresponds to the findings of *RURITAGE Del.1.1 Practices Repository* that analysed the regeneration process of 20 Role Models² around the world. Indeed, in the so-called challenge-driven Role Models (the ones belonging to the SIAs Resilience and Migration), the initial mobilised capitals are more related with human and social resources. The initial capitals are core to the regeneration process, and a good understanding of the resources of the territory is essential to undergo any action of valorisation, improvement and development.

Human Capital

Therefore, to achieve a sustainable and inclusive growth of rural areas, it is necessary to **invest in the human capital**, increasing people's knowledge, skills and motivation also in time of crisis. The tremendously fast digital transition we are living in – which has been even more emphasised by the pandemic asking for remote working, teaching and socializing – should leave no one behind and should be carefully planned in rural areas, allowing people to get the basic digital literacy to access information and activities available online. Inclusivity in this process is crucial considering the needs and the capacity of different population groups (young, elderly, women, foreigners, migrants and refugees). Moreover, enhancing human capital through education and training is central to a flourishing economy. This concerns not only the need to fill the digital divide between urban and rural areas, but also the opportunity to provide rural communities with the opportunities for educational advancement and training in field-specific skills. This could enable local business to gather new business opportunities deriving from rapidly changing customer needs (e.g. door-to-door delivery systems, new ways of promoting or selling the produced goods, etc.) or to allow new SMEs and start-ups to enter the market.

Social Capital

Secondly, a strong cooperation between institutions, families, communities, businesses, trade unions, schools, and voluntary organisations building the local **social capital** has demonstrated to be essential to react in crisis situations. Spontaneous formal and informal partnerships and agreements promoting

² RURITAGE has identified 13 Role Models at project stage, that are full partners, as rural communities that have demonstrably and successfully pursued a heritage-led rural regeneration; the end of September 2018 the project launched a call for additional RMs to gather more good practices related with the 6 SIAs through which 7 additional RMs have been selected analysed.

cooperation among the different stakeholders have allowed not only to provide solutions to cope with the emergency situation but could lead to a long-standing development. For instance, emphasizing that migrants and refugees are essential resources for the local communities due to their expertise and skills, would be a great achievement for rural communities and would support social integration and inclusion. Actions for enhancing the commitment and the capacity of employers and labour recruiters to protect migrant workers, could help in addressing the future integration of migrants in local communities.

Built Capital

The partial social restrictions or total lockdown that was experienced in some countries could have reverted citizens' priorities leaving space for 'rural renaissance', where rural areas would assume a central role in developing sustainable and resilient communities. Social distancing, the lack of adequate open public green areas and the possibility of smart working could persuade urban inhabitants to move to more natural environments. It can be viewed as an opportunity to promote rural areas as multifunctional places to live going beyond the traditional agricultural-related jobs. This opens to the possibility to repopulate those territories that have lost their inhabitants and that therefore already offer many opportunities to host newcomers, i.e. by renting or selling second houses now underutilised, thus revalorize the already existing **built capital**. This cannot be seen as a spontaneous process, since it requires local authorities to improve basic infrastructures and services, but also properly plan future development of the areas, to repopulate ageing and uninhabited rural areas but also avoiding unplanned gentrification issues.

Cultural Capital

In rural areas, intangible heritage and local traditions are one of the key assets included in **cultural capital**, reflecting the way people "know the world" and how they act within it, as well as their traditions and language. Cultural capital influences how creativity and innovation emerge and are nurtured, it is therefore a key driver for building resilient communities. Many initiatives have been promoted locally to uphold cultural capital, exploiting a great variety of the possibilities. Among these is the potential provided by digital interaction, the promotion small-scale open-air events with small audiences and the development of more flexible "menus" of art and festivals for communities. This allows adaptation to local needs, conditions and practices, allowing both opportunities for artists to perform and for locals to take part in performances. Cultural venues, that can be considered to be even more available and accessible in rural areas, can ensure a variety of cultural participation thanks to the citizens' proximity. At the same time, digital infrastructure and skills need to be strengthened in such a way to complement live experiences. Rural areas have smaller markets compared to cities but also more cultural venues and facilities per inhabitants – a crucial asset to develop proximity cultural services and tourism in time of travel restrictions (Montalto et al., 2020) and possibly also to make those opportunities permanent.

Natural Capital

At the same time, the **rich natural capital** of rural areas offers sustainable nature-based amenity functions, landscape scenery and recreation activities such as pilgrimage and hiking. Thereby, it can boost the development of a new form of slow, sustainable and proximity tourism enhancing the value of local cultural and natural heritage and human capital. The integrated management of landscape, in line with the EU New Green Deal (European Commission, 2019), will allow shaping a more sustainable future rethinking how 'to protect, conserve and enhance the EU's natural capital, and protect the health and well-being of citizens from environment-related risks and impacts. Moreover, as mentioned in the recently released EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 (European Commission, 2020b) the recent COVID-19 pandemic makes the need to protect and restore nature all the more urgent. The pandemic is raising awareness on the links between humans' and ecosystems' health. Investing in green infrastructure, wellness corridor, and slow mobility infrastructure can on the one side improve and restore natural ecosystem, but at the same time creating options for natural and cultural recreation. Last, rediscovering local food production and demanding a short and slow food chain could not just improve the quality and the health of the food we eat, but also contribute to reduce greenhouse gas emissions related with the food industry, nurturing at the same time local farmers and rural microeconomy and.

Financial Capital

Finally, **financial capital** to support this transition is essential. The COVID-19 crisis has caused a fear of widening social inequalities while revealing the crucial role of natural and cultural heritage for social cohesion, rural regeneration, and mental wellbeing. Following the pandemic, there has been a prompt response by institutions at EU national and local level to redirect funding towards the healthcare sector; this was necessary to counter the tremendous stress to which the healthcare system has been submitted, but in order to boost the re-starting of the activities it is needed to invest further in other sectors, building on this momentum to develop comprehensive heritage-led regeneration plans based on local heritage and resources. Building equitable, sustainable and inclusive rural communities will require to work on reinforcing human capital through capacity building and awareness-raising activities. Further, it will need work to ensure social and cultural capitals, re-creating and boosting the rural arts scene and working on the recognition of local heritage through bottom-up approaches. In addition, local authorities should urgently act to maintain and enhance natural capital, through a better integration of ecosystem and their services into decision making process. With this said, it is essential to continue to improve and further develop built capitals, working on essential infrastructure for mobility and fast internet connection. It is urgent to give shape to a network that will improve not only the response to crises but also the competitiveness of rural territory. In line with this, **we claim for actions at EU, national/regional and local level**. Within this document, taking reference from the Urban Agenda process³, we refer to three pillars of EU policy making and implementation:

³ <https://ec.europa.eu/futurium/en/urban-agenda-eu/what-urban-agenda-eu>

Better regulation:

As in the Urban Agenda for the EU process, we focus on more effective and coherent implementation of existing EU policies, legislation and instruments. We don't propose new regulation but rather informal contribution to the design of future and revision of existing EU regulation, in order for it to better reflect rural needs, practices and responsibilities

Better funding

We would like to contribute to identifying, supporting, integrating, and improving traditional and innovative sources of funding for rural areas at the relevant institutional level, including from European structural and investment funds (ESIF).

Better knowledge

With the knowledgebase created within RURITAGE we would like to boost evidence-based policy making. Also, in this context we refer to better knowledge in a broader sense, introducing actions that aim at improving local knowledge or skills through dedicated education or training activities.

The actions and ideas listed below raised from the participatory process described in the document, and they represent the solely vision of the authors. The European Union is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

The EU Commission is proposing to reinforce the budget for the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development. These investments could sustain and enhance local food production and the recognition of natural capital as a crucial characterizing element of rural areas. Nevertheless, there is a strong need for further integrated framework of policies and investments able to sustain such a complex environment of natural, cultural, human, social and built capitals, as intrinsic and inalienable resources of rural communities. Such a coordinated response could support the renaissance of rural areas as vibrant poles of development based on local heritage, natural resources, creativity and social inclusion as an essential baseline to regenerate rural areas and rapidly support their transition towards sustainable future. EU can go further in this aiming for effective rural regeneration and transition beyond sustainable food production through a better **integration** of other sectors:

- **Agriculture and natural services and capital** – better funding on the enhancement and protection of natural capital and services through further integration of rural communities' development within existing instruments such as the Common Agricultural Policy, the New Green Deal and the Biodiversity Strategy
- **Culture** - better funding through spread initiatives and through cohesion fund and Creative Europe in the new programming period 2021-2027. Better knowledge and further evidences, recognition and awareness raising about the role of culture as a driver of regeneration is also needed.
- **Education and training** – better knowledge to overcome the digital and entrepreneurial knowledge divide, to raise awareness on existing opportunities for business support. Better funding to support local SME in rural areas through dedicated and enhanced training

opportunities (European Social Fund, new Erasmus programme, dedicated call for rural-based SMEs within the SME Instrument)

- **Accessibility, both digital and physical** - better funding for transport, mobility and internet infrastructures to reach rural and remote areas. Initiatives such as the [WiFi4EU](#) should be further boosted and more widely spread in rural and remote areas.
- **Research and Innovation** – better funding to boost research on sustainable and inclusive rural development and to further study community resilience, services differentiation impact assessment and multicriteria analysis of participatory planning options (HorizonEurope). Also, better funding to boost innovation at local level by increasing the opportunities of cascade funding of pilot cases (Horizon Europe) to allow also small enterprises and NGOs - that might have difficulties in participating to project calls that require administrative and technical skills - to access to EU grants or dedicated call for innovation to local SME (European Regional Development Fund and European Rural Development Funds, SME instrument). Last, better knowledge on evidences that culture is a powerful driver of regeneration – economic, social and environmental – should be addressed.

Cooperation and networking: rural areas tend to feel isolated and lonesome, due to their geographical remoteness, low digital connection etc. better cooperation is crucial to identify and address common issues and exchange ideas and practices on possible solutions. While dedicated networks both for urban (EUROCITIES, ICLEI, URBACT) and specific remote rural areas (i.e EUROMONTANA, ECOLISE) already exist, it would be worth to investigate the need and the possibility of building a network of rural communities keen in working on their sustainable regeneration through their natural and cultural heritage, integrating and complementing the effective networking and cooperation already developed by ENRD for supporting the effective implementation of EU Member States' Rural Development Programmes (RDPs). The extremely high interest demonstrated in the RURITAGE project, with more than 150 organizations from all over the world responding to the different calls we launched during the project, is a clear signal of a critical mass of areas acknowledging the importance to go beyond a definition of rural development relating to *“knowledge transfer and innovation in agriculture, forestry and rural areas, to farm viability, [...], to the promotion of resource efficiency and the shift towards a low carbon economy in the agricultural, food and forestry sectors, and to promoting social inclusion, poverty reduction in and the economic development of rural areas”*⁴ for promoting an holistic and long-standing sustainable growth of rural areas capitalizing on local Cultural and Natural Heritage. Also, RURITAGE recognizes the importance of actors working in sectors other than agriculture, such as slow and sustainable tourism, migrants' integration, resilience, arts&festival, and landscape management their need of capacity building and training activities and their willingness of being involved, together with local communities, in an informal exchange of knowledge and tools for promoting rural regeneration. In line with the last point mentioned, there is the need to promote more tailored and focused actions and initiatives addressing rural areas. During the years, we have observed the growth and spread of many initiatives addressing cities, enhancing their possibilities both through dissemination and awareness raising and through specific networks and funding (Green City Capital, Creative cities initiatives, European Capital of Culture, Urban Partnership, Urban Innovative Action, etc.). It would be worth reflecting on the opportunity to enlarge the target of those initiatives including also rural areas or discussing the possibility of launching dedicated ones. So, to finally counter the traditional unbalances between rural and urban areas – where often rural areas are addressed as “minor” and less important with respect to the urban context - and to give back to rural areas a primary role for the sustainable growth of the whole EU.

⁴ Art. 4 of Regulation (EU) No 1305/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 December 2013 on support for rural development by the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD)

Actions at National/Regional level

At National/regional level there is the need of a comprehensive approach (better regulation) in line with the policies promoted at EU level. This include the followings:

- Need to guarantee **access to basic services in rural areas** (health, education, accessibility) through better funding.
- **Improving infrastructures – both digital and mobility networks** - better funding to enforce infrastructures in rural areas, in synergy with EU funds, through a digital transition allowing people to get the basic digital literacy to access information and activities available online.

Regional priorities linked to the local Smart Specialization Strategies and the Rural development Plans could work towards the reinforcement of the capitals previously mentioned - social, human, cultural, built and financial – and transversally connecting the topics included in the six RURITAGE SIAs:

- Actions for enhancing cultural and natural heritage and resources
- Actions to further boost and maintain local traditions, local arts, artefacts and festivals also creating opportunities for local businesses and creative industries and start up
- Actions to boost human and social capital (elderly, young, women, migrants and refugees) working on long lasting community's resilience.
- Actions to develop human capital through dedicated trainings and studying and learning opportunities

Actions at Local level

In line with the LEADER and the RURITAGE approaches, local authorities should boost the role of the communities in the development of sustainable regeneration strategies, exploiting local resources and capitals. A full recognition of the role of local stakeholders, communities and civil society is needed together with a well-established strategy to implement community participatory process. This process could take inspiration from the LEADER approach and from Del 2.1 RURITAGE methodology for Community-based Heritage Management and Planning (CHMP)⁵ that include a step by step guide to co-develop, implement and monitor rural regeneration strategy with local communities. Diversification of the approaches, involving all the 6 SIAs, is needed and included in CHMP just presented.

Also, the role of local administrations and stakeholders is crucial in the rural regeneration process to properly plan future development of the areas, to create favourable conditions to repopulate ageing and uninhabited rural areas avoiding unplanned gentrification issues – tourism, second home, and staycations can contribute to rural regeneration but should be properly planned and regulated.

⁵ <https://www.ruritage.eu/resources/publications/>

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Policy brief

Deliverable 7.5

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Thinking beyond the COVID-19 crisis: heritage-based opportunities for the regeneration of rural areas

RURITAGE
Heritage for Rural Regeneration

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Introduction

The Covid-19 pandemic is considerably threatening rural areas, posing challenges exacerbated by low available financial resources, inaccessible health and public services and greater physical and digital isolation. At the same time, the lockdown experienced in many countries has often led to rural areas being considered as safe shelters, characterised by an easy to maintain social distancing and higher access to nature-based recreational activities; that are crucial for maintaining social cohesion and mental wellbeing and for enhancing local development.

RURITAGE bases its regeneration methodology on local heritage resources, perceiving heritage in its wider sense, beyond tangible monuments and landscapes. Further it recognises intangible forms of traditions, social practices, and knowledge as the values that tie communities together and as a resource for sustainable local development. The paradigm for regenerating rural communities lies in the identification of six powerful drivers that boost regeneration in rural communities. These six drivers identified in the project are the RURITAGE Systemic Innovation Areas (SIAs), Pilgrimage, Local Food Production, Art and Festivals, Landscape Management, Migration and Resilience.

Building upon the RURITAGE narrative, this Policy brief summarises how the new challenges posed in rural areas by the COVID-19 pandemic can be turned into **opportunities for the sustainable growth of rural communities in the future**. Furthermore, it approaches the multidimensional topic by focusing on recommendations divided into **six different capitals**: natural, cultural, social, human, built and financial.

The insights and recommendations summarised in this deliverable are based on three activities arranged by RURITAGE:

- An open call for actions was launched in April 2020 to collect practices to increase and strengthen resilience in rural communities. The call was open between April and mid-June. In total, it collected 66 actions from all round the world.
- A participatory workshop took place during the RURITAGE General Assembly on May 28th, 2020. All project partners discussed challenges and opportunities for the future of rural areas during the session.
- A public webinar on the 8th of July 2020 to present preliminary results based on above work and to further discuss them with EU institutions and relevant actors within rural development (Eu Commission, CoE, ENRD).

Foundations for comprehensive responses to COVID-19 challenges

Rural areas are facing challenges exacerbated by less available resources and greater isolation issues. Rural communities struggle in finding tailored solutions for their already fragile environments. However, rural areas are responding to the challenges posed by COVID-19 by reinforced networks, better collaboration, and solidarity for strengthened resilience. They are showing that co-operation was and is essential. What is now emerging is a better understanding of local community needs to use and manage capitals in an integrated way to achieve sustainable and inclusive growth of rural areas.

Human Capital

- **Increase people's knowledge, skills and motivation** also in time of crisis.
- **Leave no one behind** by carefully planning the digital transition in rural areas, allowing different population groups to receive basic digital literacy to access information and activities available online.
- **Bridge the digital divide** between urban and rural areas
- Provide rural communities with **field training** to enable new business opportunities deriving from rapidly changing customer needs and to allow new SMEs and start-ups to enter the market.
- Properly plan future sustainable development of rural areas, to **repopulate ageing and scarcely rural areas while avoiding unplanned gentrification issues**.
- Develop sustainable and resilient communities while **integrating urban inhabitants interested in moving to rural areas**.

Social Capital

- **Strong cooperation** between institutions, communities, businesses, trade unions, schools, and voluntary organisations.
- **Promote formal and informal partnerships** to cope with the emergency while leading to a long-standing development.
- **Strengthen solidarity and reinforce vulnerable**

groups; women, elderly, young and children, persons with reduced mobility, and ethnic minorities, by assuring less isolation access to services.

- In addition, **enhance the commitment and the capacity of employers and recruiters to protect migrant workers**, thus helping to address the future integration of migrants into local communities.

Built Capital

- Promote rural areas as **multifunctional places to live in**, beyond the traditional agricultural-related jobs and to further enable remote working.
- Improve **transport, mobility and digital infrastructures**.

Cultural Capital

- **Exploit digital interaction** and promote small-scale **open-air events** with smaller audiences, also cooperating locally for using school playgrounds, fields, etc.
- **Encourage adaptation to local needs** and practices by developing more flexible “menus” of arts and festivals, while allowing opportunities for artists to perform and for locals to take part in performances.
- **Ensure a variety of cultural participation opportunities** thanks to the availability of cultural venues and citizens’ proximity.

Financial Capital

- Even if the pandemic obviously claims for **investments in the healthcare sector**, a comprehensive response to the crisis also **needs to address other sectors, sustaining holistic strategies** for the heritage-led regeneration of rural territories.
- **Improve the long-term competitiveness of rural territories**.

Natural Capital

- Reinforce environmental sustainability through raised awareness of **interconnections between human and ecosystem health**. By strengthening the understanding of local heritage, and **inhabitants will further value and care for their surrounding environment**.
- Use cultural and natural heritage as a driver to develop new forms of **slow, sustainable and proximity tourism to further boost local economy**.
- **Invest in green infrastructure, and slow mobility infrastructure** for improving and restoring natural ecosystems, while creating options for natural and cultural recreation.
- **Rediscover local food production** thus improving the quality and the health of the food we eat, but also contributing to reduce greenhouse gas emissions related with the food industry, and simultaneously, supporting local farmers and rural microeconomy.

Actions and recommendations for thinking beyond the COVID-19 crisis in rural areas

Actions and recommendations for thinking beyond the COVID-19 crisis in rural areas refer to three different areas of improvement:

- **Policy:** a need for more effective and coherent implementation of existing EU policies, legislation and instruments. We do not propose new regulations, rather informal revisions of existing ones, to better meet rural needs, practices, responsibilities, continue networking efforts and feedback from the stakeholders implementing policies on the ground, in line ENRD work.
- **Funding:** A need to identify, support, integrate and improve existing, as well as innovative sources of funding for rural areas at the relevant institutional level, including European Structural and Investment Funds (ESIF), promoting a strategic approach for ensuring synergies among the different funding tools and policies, at the EU level as well as at the national and regional level, and for avoiding duplications.
- **Knowledge:** A need to boost evidence-based policy making working on capacity building at local level and to introduce actions that aim to improve local knowledge or skills through dedicated education and training activities.

There is a strong need for a **fully integrated framework of policies and investments** able to sustain such a complex environment of natural, cultural, human, social, and built capitals. To **support the renaissance of rural areas** as vibrant hubs of development based on local heritage, natural resources, creativity and social inclusion, the EU should boost an effective rural regeneration and transition beyond sustainable food production through a better integration of other sectors. The recommendations address the six capitals addressed before and are applicable at three different levels; EU, national/regional and local level, as follows:

Actions at EU level

- **Rural Development Programme (RDP) should support diversification of jobs and incomes** of rural communities by dedicating funding to local heritage and cultural sector activities that contribute to sustainable development of rural areas.
- **Agriculture and natural services and capital:** funding for the enhancement and protection of natural capital and services, also in terms of nature-based tourism, should be better integrated with existing instruments and related funding streams such as the the New Green Deal and the Biodiversity Strategy.

- **Culture:** better integration of funding coming from cohesion funds and Creative Europe in the new programming period 2021-2027. Boost the integration of culture into the regional smart specialization strategies (RIS3).

- **Accessibility, both digital and physical:** dedicated funding scheme for transport, mobility and digital infrastructures to reach rural and remote areas and to improve their accessibility. Initiatives such as the WiFi4EU should be further boosted and more widely spread in rural and remote areas.

- **Education and training:** promote initiatives to overcome the digital and entrepreneurial divide, to raise awareness of existing opportunities for business support. Support local SME in rural areas through funding for accessing to dedicated and enhanced training opportunities through the European Social Fund, the new Erasmus programme, or dedicated call for rural-based SMEs within the SME Instrument.

- **Research and Innovation:** boost research on sustainable and inclusive rural development and further study community resilience, services differentiation impact assessment and multi-criteria analysis of participatory planning options (Horizon Europe). Boost innovation at local level by increasing the opportunities of cascade funding of pilot cases (Horizon Europe) to allow also small enterprises and NGOs to access to EU grants or dedicated call for innovation to local SME (European Regional Development Fund and European Rural Development Funds, SME instrument). Provide new evidences about culture as a powerful driver of regeneration – economic, social and environmental.

Moreover, RURITAGE highlights a need to **enlarge the scope of the many initiatives addressing cities** (e.g. Green City Capital, Creative cities initiatives, European Capital of Culture, Urban Innovative Action) to include rural areas or possibly launching dedicated ones. RURITAGE calls for a better cooperation to identify and address common issues and exchange ideas and practices. By building a network of rural communities keen on working on sustainable regeneration through natural and cultural heritage, RURITAGE aims to integrate and complement the effective networking and cooperation with European Network for Rural Development (ENRD) along with other European initiatives.

Actions at national/regional level

There is the need for a comprehensive approach in line with the policies promoted at EU level:

- **Guarantee access to basic services** in rural areas (health, education, accessibility) through better funding.
- **Improve infrastructures – both digital and mobili-**

ty: toned to enforce infrastructures in rural areas, in synergy with EU funds, through a fair digital transition allowing people to get the basic digital literacy to access information and activities online.

- **Integrate regional priorities, embedded into the Regional operational programme, the rural development plans and the RIS3 strategy** to work towards the reinforcement of the social, human, cultural, natural, built and financial capitals and transversally connecting RURITAGE System Innovation Areas, further boosting and maintaining local traditions, local arts, artefacts and festivals, boosting human and social capital.

Actions on local level

- **Boost the role of the communities** in the development of sustainable regeneration strategies, exploiting local resources and capitals, in line with the LEADER and the RURITAGE approaches.

- **Enhance the role of local administrations and stakeholders** to properly plan future development of the areas, to create favourable conditions to repopulate ageing and sparsely populated areas.

- **Aid participatory approaches** to strengthen local solidarity and cooperation, to further join forces for increased resilience.

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